

EDITORIAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING INFORMATION CULTURE IN STUDENTS

H.O. Abdusamatovna

Senior Lecturer of Termez State University of Engineering and Agrotechnologies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17538813>

Abstract. *In this article, the term "shaping information culture" is used to refer to the humanization of value orientations and points of view, determined (determined) by the interaction of specific business factors and external conditions, the subject of editorial activity, knowledge in the information environment, interaction, mutual relations, activity, the development of a lifestyle based on information, The article covers approaches to the understanding of information as an artificial-natural process of individual changes aimed at the creation, storage, processing, distribution and consumption of information as an object of culture.*

Keywords: *information, culture, activity, renewal, problems. globalization, communication, technologies, technological, media, artificial-natural.*

Introduction. The idea that education should be carried out in harmony with nature originated in ancient times and was reflected in the works of Democritus, Plato, and Aristotle. This principle was later systematized by the 17th-century scholar John Amos Comenius. Its essence is as follows: natural factors play a crucial role in the development (progress) of a human being. Therefore, in creating conditions for development, it is necessary to treat a person as a part of nature, relying on his or her innate capacities and natural potential. In other words, in organizing any kind of activity—including information-related activity—it is essential to take into account the learners' natural abilities, since "where abilities do not lead the way, effort is in vain; struggling against nature is futile."

The activity organized within the framework of higher education must be aimed at both the explicit and latent potentials of students. This approach ensures that the integrity of the learners' inner world is harmoniously connected with external educational influences. The realization of this process in extracurricular circles (or online learning environments) requires a differentiated and individualized approach, which offers the learner the opportunity of choice and self-expression. Logically, this leads us to the next pedagogical principle.

The Principle of Pedagogical Management. Within the context of an Internet-based educational environment, pedagogical management can be understood as the process of directing the development of students' personal potential. Management, as a functional activity, involves maintaining the structure of the organized system, supporting its plan of action, implementing the program, and ensuring the achievement of goals [48; 52; 74; 94; 124]. The organizer of the process performs a set of general management functions such as goal-setting, analysis, planning, decision-making, organization of actions, coordination, and regulation. Among the specific tasks of management is pedagogical motivation (encouragement). We agree with A. L. Umansky, who defined pedagogical encouragement as "the creation of motivational conditions for an individual's socially significant activity."

The Principle of Cultural Conformity. Formulated in the 19th century, this principle emphasizes that education must be based on universal human values and correspond to the cultural

norms that do not contradict them. In the process of developing information culture, learners should become acquainted with the different layers of culture, society, and the world, adapt to continuous changes within themselves and their surroundings, and learn to mitigate the negative consequences of innovations. From the standpoint of applying the principle of cultural conformity to the development of information culture, education should be carried out in accordance with culture itself. This means familiarizing students with all the achievements and benefits of human culture, including its heritage—science, technology, technological progress, general culture, and social values. Researchers such as V. M. Bim-Bad, A. V. Petrovsky, and others emphasize that in modern education, the main focus of teaching methods and forms has shifted from memorizing facts to experiencing and comprehending reality, and to applying the culture being studied to solve personal problems.

The principle of the cultural approach is based on understanding the deep interaction between the categories of *information* and *culture*, and on the idea that information culture constitutes an integral part of a person's general culture. From this perspective, information culture shapes a person's worldview, determines their goals and objectives, and fosters the development of value orientations toward information as a cultural element. Moreover, it prevents the dehumanization and replacement of spiritual values that may occur as a result of the unprecedented growth and development of scientific, technological, and informational achievements in the information society.

The principle of dialogic interaction between teachers and students presupposes that, within the context of higher education and Internet-based learning environments, the process of social and educational activity should be organized according to the capabilities and potential of the students. Collaboration and dialogue between teachers and learners should form the foundation of their mutual activity. Even when conducted within a group, dialogue must remain personally oriented toward each participant, ensuring their active and meaningful engagement. Summarizing the above principles, it should be emphasized that they represent the key requirements and fundamental rules of the process we are organizing. The process of developing students' information culture should be designed on the basis of systemic, activity-based, technological, and integrative approaches.

We applied the systemic approach to construct the theoretical framework of the research subject, to synthesize various forms of knowledge about the discipline, to define the content of the formation of information culture, and to substantiate the pedagogical conditions for its modeling. The systemic approach makes it possible to understand the integrity of the phenomenon of information culture and to overcome the fragmentation of methodological bases in studying its traditional components—such as information technologies, network communication culture, and computer literacy. This approach also enables the achievement of a new qualitative level, consistent with the thesis that “the whole is greater than the sum of its parts.” It allows for expressing the concept of *information culture* as a key condition for effective activity in addressing the problem of students' preparedness in the field of information education. The essence of the systemic approach lies in identifying the properties of system objects and improving them, which is reflected in the following pedagogical principles and regularities.

a) The integrity of the system in relation to its external environment means that the system is studied together with its environment. From this perspective, educational issues form an independent scope of problems but are studied in close connection with social and economic development and the requirements of society.

b) Dividing the whole into structural parts that lead to the isolation of its elements. The properties of the elements depend on their belonging to a particular system, and the properties of the system are not determined (or limited) by the properties or the sum of its elements.

c) It is necessary to identify the most important element (the defining one) in the system, called the “connection” that forms the system. In an “open” educational system, the relationships between the individual and various educational conditions and sources act as this connection, while in a “closed” educational system, the relationship between the “educator and the learner” serves this role.

d) The set of elements represents the structure and organization of the system objects. These concepts express the orderliness of the system, the interconnection, and interdependence of its elements. For example, in any goal-oriented system, including pedagogical ones, the categories reflecting its main elements are: goals–content–conditions–means–ways of implementation and development–results.

e) A special method of regulating the relationships between system elements is management, which includes goal setting, selection of means, monitoring results, and making corrections (adjustments).

The activity-based approach was applied to ensure the functioning laws of the pedagogical model, to shape the student’s skills and upbringing, and to implement the step-by-step and continuous process of forming students’ information culture in the Internet clubs at schools. The principle of the activity-based approach means that the formation of students’ information culture should be constructed not from the perspective of a librarian explaining how a library, information service, or computer works, or familiarizing learners with the technical details of computer technology, but rather from the perspective of the consumer or user. It should be based on the informational tasks that such individuals need to solve in the course of their educational, professional, or leisure activities.

The activity-based approach involves studying the real process of students’ interaction with the surrounding environment and ensures the solution of significant life tasks. In this case, a person acts as a subject of interaction, performing various sequences of actions and serving as an active principle (source of activity). From the perspective of applying the activity-based approach to the problem of forming information culture, this approach aims to reveal the essence and structure of such culture by identifying and describing the methods of action that lead students toward the effective acquisition of relevant knowledge. At the same time, mastering knowledge involves consolidating certain actions and acquiring new ones that mediate the development of students’ general abilities and behavioral patterns. Knowledge is not merely transmitted; it is acquired by learners in the process of their own activity. In the course of implementing such activity, the ability to meaningfully analyze and design the outcomes of the activity becomes especially significant.

The principle of the technological approach makes it possible to view the process of forming students’ information culture as a pedagogical technology that encompasses a set of methods and means aimed at achieving the desired result. This principle requires defining the final outcome in detail and establishing mandatory control to obtain results that meet specified parameters. The process of forming students’ information culture can be considered technological only if:

– it is guided by a clearly defined goal, activity program, and a sequence of actions (curriculum) that lead to achieving the goal;

– there are available means of implementing the set goals (educational, methodological, technical, etc.);

– at each stage, there are established requirements for the final product (knowledge and skills);

– there exist measurement tools (tests, assignments, etc.) to evaluate the level of information culture.

To ensure the success of the students' learning process, we applied a comprehensive approach, which encompasses:

– influencing various domains of students' development (cognitive–worldview, emotional–volitional, creative–practical);

– taking into account all spheres of personal life (family, classroom, educational institutions, etc.);

– using diverse teaching and educational methods and tools.

At the Internet club functioning under the higher educational institution as an educational and upbringing organization, we relied on the above-mentioned principles and approaches to form students' information culture and identified the pedagogical conditions that ensure the effectiveness of this process. Thus, by *pedagogical conditions*, the author proposes to understand the situational factors and circumstances that influence (and are reflected in) the achievement of the desired outcome. The research makes it possible to identify the following age-specific characteristics of students:

– an increased need for social self-expression and independence;

– orientation toward the future, including lifestyle, professional choice, and role models (the need for self-respect and self-determination);

– striving for cooperation with adults;

– strengthening the role of pragmatic motivation in one's actions.

At this age, abstract-logical thinking develops, and perceptions about the world become more profound, which in turn helps to shape a person's information culture. The main activity of the Internet club, due to the specific features of its subject (science or topic), attracts children interested in computer and new information technologies. Within this approach (accordingly), the organization where students and teachers can adhere to the following concepts, conditions, and principles is considered effective:

- mutual trust among all participants in the pedagogical process;
- adherence to all moral and ethical standards;
- joint development of educational goals and collective participation in achieving them. Naturally, everyone does this according to their skills and level of knowledge, but everyone's opinion is taken into account and discussed;
- students' and teachers' understanding of their participation in solving higher education issues and organizing work;
- continuous activities (discussions, reflections) aimed at ensuring a shared understanding of educational values within the institution;
- cooperation and mutual communication between students and teachers;
- working based on dialogue and discussion as a learning method;
- active participation of all in freely coordinated educational activities leading to the intended results.

The “higher education community” is considered a real way to build a new type of society. This does not require global structural changes or significant financial expenses, yet the result is democratic, characterized by “family-like” mutual relations, which may serve as a real model of social interaction for students in general society. Thus, the value of information largely depends on the method of obtaining it and the specific situation in which it is applied.

Figure 1. The Objective Need for Information Resources.

It is impossible to directly transfer the vast experience available in other countries to the higher education institutions of our country, since the formation of a community largely depends on the national and social characteristics of a particular country and region. Therefore, it cannot be simply copied from one country to another. However, ignoring it, failing to analyze it, and not implementing its scientifically grounded adaptation would also be a mistake. The study of social psychology and communication psychology helps teachers change their perspectives (positions) and their methods of communication with students. The achievements of management and educational psychology assist school principals in transforming their work with teaching and student groups.

In our experimental research, this condition was ensured through the use of individual and group project tasks within methodological technologies (developing and regularly updating Internet websites and pages, creating electronic presentations, test applications, educational support programs for various subjects, design projects, and others). This also included collecting, processing, and publishing information about events, plans, and achievements in higher education on the Internet. Furthermore, the members of the club provided individual assistance to other students in preparing essays and creative works, getting ready for subject Olympiads, searching for information, and participating in distance contests and educational formats. This helped draw students' attention to the social significance of informational activity, develop their information needs and interests, and assist them in determining their future professional orientation. On the other hand, increasing the status of Internet club members within the community and promoting informational activity contributed to effective use of the opportunities offered by global networks.

REFERENCES

1. Arnol'dov, A.I. *Modern Cultural Policy: From Idea to Practice*. In: Arnol'dov A.I., Lazareva A.N., Balagushkin E.G. *Introduction to Cultural Studies: Lecture Course*. Moscow, 1993, pp. 9–43.
2. Belkin, A.S. *Fundamentals of Age Pedagogy*. Moscow: Akademiya, 2000, 192 p.

3. Bell, D. *The Coming of Post-Industrial Society: A Venture in Social Forecasting*. Moscow: Academia, 1999, 956 p.
4. Beshenkov, S.A. *Modeling and Formalization: Methodological Manual*. Moscow: Laboratory of Basic Knowledge, 2002, 333 p.
5. Vendrovskaya, R.B. "Educational System of the 1920s." In: *Humanistic Educational Systems Yesterday and Today (in Descriptions by Their Authors and Researchers)*. Moscow: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 1998, pp. 137–142.
6. Voinova, N.A., Voinov, A.V. "Features of the Formation of Information Competence of University Students." *Innovations in Education*, 2004, No. 4, p. 111.
7. Glikman, I.Z. "Education and Upbringing." *Pedagogy*, 1999, No. 2, pp. 110–115.
Grechikhin, A.A. "Information Culture: An Attempt at Typological Definition." In: *Problems of Information Culture: Collection of Articles*. Ed. by Yu.S. Zubov, I.M. Andreeva. Moscow, 1994, p. 15.
8. Sultanova, O'.N. "Use of New Pedagogical Technology in Physics Lessons and Class Activities." *Vyshshaya Shkola*, December 23, 2018, pp. 255–258.
9. Sultanova, O'.N. "Students' Competence-Based Approach to Solving Experimental and Graphical Problems in Physics." *International Interdisciplinary Research*, Vol. 9, May 2021, pp. 903–908.
10. Sultanova, O'.N. "Independent Learning of Students on the Basis of Competence-Based Approach as a Guarantee of High Efficiency." *International Journal of Advanced Research*, CrossRef Indexed, Journal Impact Factor 7.445, Vol. 7, Issue 12, December 12, 2019, pp. 16–22. www.journalijar.com